

GRAPHITE NANOPATELETS AS NANO-REINFORCEMENTS FOR POLYMERS: COMPARISON BETWEEN A THERMOSET AND A THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX

Kyriaki Kalaitzidou, Hiroyuki Fukushima and Lawrence T. Drzal
*Department of Chemical Engineering and Materials Science
Composite Materials and Structure Center, Michigan State University
East Lansing MI, 48824-1226, USA*

ABSTRACT: Graphite is the stiffest material found in nature (Young's Modulus = 1060 MPa) with a modulus several times that of clay and with excellent thermal and electrical conductivity which allows the use of graphite composites not only in structural but in thermal and electrical applications as well. The objective of this study is the comparison between the epoxy-graphite and the thermoplastic-graphite nanocomposites. In addition, the graphite-reinforced polymers are compared to composites made with commercially available carbon reinforcing materials i.e., PAN based carbon fiber, Vapor Grown Carbon Fiber (VGCF), and Nanoscopic High-structure Carbon Black. Prior to the fabrication of the composites a special thermal treatment was applied to the graphite flakes to produce exfoliated graphite reinforcements. The X-ray Diffraction (XRD) and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) results indicated that the graphite flakes were well-exfoliated to achieve nanoplatelets with thickness of 20 nm or less. The nanocomposite was fabricated by combining the exfoliated graphite flakes with an amine-epoxy resin. An appropriate surface treatment established for the new material that improved the adhesion between the graphite platelets and the polymer matrix resulted in an improvement of the mechanical properties of the composite material. In the case of the thermoplastic matrix the resin and the graphite platelets were fed into a mixing extruder and injection molded. The mechanical properties of these composites were investigated by flexural testing. Their glass transition temperature (T_g) was determined by Differential Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA) and the coefficient of thermal expansion was examined by Thermal Mechanical Analysis (TMA). The electrical conductivity was investigated by impedance measurements using the 2-probe method. Flexural tests results show that nanocomposite materials made with these nanographite platelets have higher strength and modulus than that of composites made with commercially available carbon reinforcing materials. In case of the graphite/epoxy system, impedance measurements show that the exfoliated graphite platelets percolate at below 3 volume percent, which is better than carbon fiber and comparable with other carbon materials, and exhibit a ~10 order of magnitude reduction in impedance at these concentrations. This indicates that the graphite nanocomposites can be used in new applications such as electrostatic dissipation and electro magnetic interference shielding.

KEYWORDS: nanoplatelets, graphite, nanocomposite, electrical conductive fillers, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Fibers and platelets with dimensions in the micron range are used at loading levels between 15 and 60% to enhance the mechanical properties of polymeric materials. Unfortunately, these high loading levels harm other mechanical and thermal properties and make processing very difficult [1-3]. In contrast to traditional fillers, nanofillers i.e., exfoliated clays are expected to be effective at a loading under 5% by weight, introducing only a minor increase in materials cost. They provide significant improvement in

modulus, thermal and dimensional stability, surface hardness and barrier properties which make these materials primary candidates for a variety of applications especially in automotive industry [4]. The majority of the research in the field of nanocomposites is focused on clay nanocomposites produced by incorporating nanometer-size clay particles in polymers such as polypropylene, polyethylene, epoxies etc. [5]. However, the clay nanocomposites lack electrical and thermal conductivity that limits their potential applications. On the other hand if conductive nano-size fillers i.e., carbon black or graphite flakes, are used instead, then nanocomposites can be used not only as structural materials but also in other applications such as electrostatic dissipation (ED), electromagnetic and radio frequency interference (EMI, RI), and heat dissipation.

Graphite is one of the stiffest materials found in nature (Young's Modulus ~ 1060 Gpa) with excellent electrical and thermal conductivity. It has better mechanical, thermal and electrical properties and lower density compare to clays [1,6]. This led researchers to apply the clay nano-reinforcement concept to graphite, which also has layered structure, to produce graphite-polymer nanocomposites. The two main fabrication techniques for the graphite nanocomposites are the *in-situ* polymerization with expanded graphite (*in-situ* polymerization technique), [7-9], and the *in-situ* polymerization with initiator-intercalated graphite (polymerization-filling technique), [10,11]. The lower cost of crystalline graphite (\$1.5-1.6/lb and less than \$5/lb for the graphite nanoplatelets), compare to other conductive fillers, such as Carbon Nanotubes (\sim \$100/g), Vapor Growth Carbon Fibers, VGCF, (\$40-50/lb) and carbon fibers (\sim \$5-6/lb), as well as, graphite's superior mechanical properties compare to those of carbon black (\sim \$0.5/lb) makes graphite a more realistic choice for commercial applications that require both mechanical strengthening and electrical conductivity of the final product. The key point in utilizing the superior properties of graphite particles is sufficient exfoliation, which will result in separation into single or few layers of graphene sheets and an appropriate surface treatment, which will improve the adhesion between the graphite platelets and the polymer matrix resulted in strengthening of the composite material.

The objective of this research is to design and fabricate nanocomposites composed of polymer matrices reinforced with exfoliated graphite nano-platelets and determine their mechanical, thermal and electrical properties. The goal of this study is two fold: (i) Comparison between an epoxy-graphite and a thermoplastic-graphite composite and (ii) Comparison between the graphite-reinforced polymers with composites made with commercially available carbon reinforcing materials, i.e., Nanoscopic high-structure Carbon Black, Vapor Growth Carbon Fiber and PAN based carbon fiber. A special thermal treatment was applied to exfoliate the graphite flakes, which afterwards were milled in order to obtain the nano-size reinforcements. In the case of the graphite-epoxy composites a special surface treatment of the graphite nano-platelets was applied that improved the adhesion between the graphite flakes and the epoxy matrix. At this point, no surface treatment was necessary for the graphite-polypropylene composites. It was found that addition of graphite nanoplatelets at a loading level of 3% vol resulted in a significant increase in the modulus of elasticity in both the graphite-epoxy and the graphite-polypropylene systems while at the same time the flexural strength improved in both systems with the most drastic increase observed in the case of graphite-polypropylene composites. Flexural tests also showed that nanocomposite materials made with these nanographite platelets have higher strength and modulus than that of composites made with commercially available carbon reinforcing materials. Decrease in the Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) at both, the below T_g and the above T_g, conditions was observed for both the epoxy and polypropylene graphite-nanocomposites which was comparable and in some cases higher than the decrease in CTE due to other conductive fillers. Finally, the electrical conductivity of the graphite nanocomposites was investigated and the percolation threshold was determined for the graphite-epoxy systems.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: All the materials used in this study are commercially available. The PP with the trade name Pro-fax 6301 (melt flow index 12 g/10min, ASTM D1238) was donated by Basell. The epoxy used was diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (EPON 828) was purchased from the Shell Chemical Co and Jeffamine T403 from Huntsman Petrochemical was used as the curing agent for this epoxy. Graphite Intercalated Compounds (GICs) were obtained from UCAR International Inc. The control carbon materials were (i) PAN based carbon fiber (PANEX 33 MC Milled Carbon Fibers, Zoltek Co), (ii) Vapor Growth Carbon Fiber or VGCF (Pyrograf III, PR-19 PS grade, Pyrograf Products, Inc.) and (iii) Nanosize High Structure carbon black (KETJENBLACK EC-600 JD, Akzo Novel Polymer Chemicals LLC). The basic characteristics of these materials and their ESEM images are shown in Table 1 and Figure 1 respectively.

Table 1: Geometrical and Surface Characteristics of Conductive Fillers

Material	Length/thickness (um)	Diameter (nm)	Aspect Ratio	Surface Area (m ² /g)	Density (g/cm ³)
Graphite (processed)	0.011	860	~77	94	2
CF	175	7200	~24	16	1.81
VGCF	50-100	150	333-666	25	2
Carbon Black	0.4-0.5	400-500	1	1400	1.8

Figure 1: ESEM Images of (i) Chopped Carbon Fiber, (ii) Milled VGCF and (iii) Nano-size Carbon Black

Processing of Graphite: A special thermal treatment was applied to the intercalated graphite. Significant expansion of the graphite flakes due to the vaporization of the intercalated acid in the graphite galleries was observed. The expanded graphite flakes were pulverized using an ultrasonic processor and milled using a vibratory mill. The TEM images of graphite nanoplatelets are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: TEM Images of the new nano-graphite material, the scale bars are 50nm (left) and 5nm (right)

Graphite-Epoxy Composite Fabrication: The reinforcement was added to DGEBA and mixed using an ultrasonic homogenizer for 5 minutes. Then stoichiometric amount of Jeffamine T403 (DGEBA/Jeffamine was 100/45) was added and mixed at room temperature. The system was outgassed to reduce the voids and cured at 85 °C for 2 hours, followed by post curing at 150 °C for 2 hours. It is noted that a surface treatment was applied at the graphite nano-platelets, prior to mixing with the epoxy resin, which resulted in acrylamide grafting of the graphite, in order to improve the adhesion and enhance the mechanical properties.

Graphite-Polypropylene Composite Fabrication: The nanocomposite samples were melt-blended in a DSM Micro 15 Compounder, (vertical, co-rotating twin-screw microextruder) at 180 °C for 3 minutes at a screw speed of 200rpms. The composite material was molded into flexural bars using a Daga Micro Injector where the cylinder temperature was 180 °C and the mold temperature was 50 °C. An injection pressure of 100psi was used. No surface treatment was applied at the graphite nano-platelets.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Mechanical Properties: Flexural Strength and Modulus

Flexural test was performed using UTS machine [United Calibration Corp.] at room temperature following ASTM D790 standard test method. In case of the epoxy composites the samples were made in standard bar shape molds and polished carefully in order to obtain a constant throughout the sample thickness. There was no need for polishing in case of the polypropylene composites because the injection molding process resulted in samples with homogeneous dimensions. The test was performed at a strain rate of 0.05 in/minute.

Figure 3 shows the flexural strength and the modulus of elasticity for the various polypropylene composite systems at loading levels of 0, 1, 2 and 3 vol%. As shown in Figure 3, the addition of just 3 vol% of the graphite nano-platelets resulted in ~30% increase of the flexural strength and in ~70% increase of the modulus compare to that of the neat polypropylene. All the conductive fillers improved both the strength and the modulus but the graphite nano-platelets had a more profound effect especially in the modulus.

Figure 3: Flexural strength and modulus of elasticity for carbon reinforced polypropylene composites

Figure 4 shows the flexural properties of epoxy-based composites. As in the case of the polypropylene composites mentioned above, four different conductive fillers were used at three loading levels. Again the graphite nano-platelets proved to be the best reinforcement compared to carbon black, VGCF and PAN based carbon fibers. Addition of 3 vol% graphite in the epoxy resulted in a ~12% increase in strength and ~22% increase in modulus.

Figure 4: Flexural strength and modulus of elasticity for carbon reinforced polypropylene composites

2. Thermal Properties Coefficient of Thermal Expansion)

The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of both the polypropylene-based and the epoxy-based systems reinforced with the four conductive fillers mention above, at a loading level of 3vol% were determined by TMA for both the below the glass transition temperature (below Tg) and the above glass transition temperature (above Tg) regime. The results are shown in Figures 6 through 8.

In the polypropylene-based composites the CTE was measured along two directions, the transverse, which is the direction perpendicular to the direction that the polymer melt flows into the mold, and the longitudinal, which is the direction along the flow. The samples for the CTE measurements were cut out from the flexural bar as shown in Figure 5. Samples A were used for measuring the CTE in the transverse direction and samples B for measuring along the flow direction.

Figure 5: Position of the samples used for determination of CTE

As shown in Figure 6, decrease of the CTE along the longitudinal direction was observed for all the fillers at both below and above Tg. In particular, for the below Tg regime, the graphite nano-platelets had the same effect with VGCF and PAN based carbon fibers, resulted in ~25% decrease of CTE. For the above Tg regime, graphite had the same effect as carbon black and VGCF (~40% decrease) but PAN based carbon fiber had a more profound effect.

Figure 6: Coefficient of thermal expansion for polypropylene-based composites along the flow direction

The same trend was observed also in the measurements of CTE along the transverse direction as shown in Figure 7. The graphite nanoplatelets resulted in a decrease of CTE of the order of 15-20% . A similar decrease was observed also due to VGCF.

Figure 7: Coefficient of thermal expansion for polypropylene-based composites along the flow direction

In the epoxy-composites the acrylamide grafted nanographite showed the lowest CTE, A decrease of ~22% for the below Tg condition and ~7% for the above Tg condition was observed as shown in Figure 8 indicating good dispersion and strong bonding between the nanoreinforcements and the matrix.

Figure 8: Coefficient of thermal expansion for epoxy-based composites along the flow direction

3. Electrical Properties: Threshold Value and Electrical Conductivity

In case of the graphite/epoxy system, impedance measurements show that the exfoliated graphite platelets percolate around 1 volume percent, which is better than carbon fiber and comparable with other carbon materials, and exhibit a ~10 order of magnitude reduction in impedance at these concentrations [13]. This indicates that the graphite nanocomposites can be used in new applications such as electrostatic dissipation and electro magnetic interference shielding.

The polypropylene-based composites did not show any conductivity for loading levels of up to 10 vol%. Only the 10vol% carbon black/polypropylene samples were found to be conductive. It was also observed that the 3vol% carbon black reinforced samples were conductive before injection molding but not after. This indicated that the orientation of the fillers occurred during the injection molding does not allow the particles or the fibers to form a continuous network which explains the lack of conductivity in the molded part. To further investigate this assumption the fracture surface of the 10 vol% PAN based carbon fiber/polypropylene and 10vol% VGCF/polypropylene samples were examined using ESEM. As expected

the fibers near the edges of the fracture surface were oriented normal to the surface while the fibers in the middle had a random orientation. A schematic figure of the fiber orientation in the fracture surface is shown in Figure 9. The surface as shown, is perpendicular to the flow direction.

Figure 9: Fiber orientation in a fracture surface of injection molded samples

Figures 10 and 11 are the ESEM images of 10 vol% PAN based Carbon fiber/PP and 10 vol% VGCF/PP fracture surfaces. The samples were treated with O₂ Plasma for 10min and gold coated. The left images correspond to the “edge region” and the right images to the “middle region” of Figure 9.

Figure 10: ESEM images of 10vol% VGCF/PP composite (i) edge area, (ii) middle area

Figure 11: ESEM images of 10vol% VGCF/PP composite (i) edge area, (ii) middle area

CONCLUSIONS

A new nanoplatelet graphite material was developed by exfoliation of graphite. This material was used as reinforcement in both an epoxy and a polypropylene system and the mechanical, thermal and electrical properties of the graphite nanocomposites were investigated in both cases. In addition, for comparison, composites using commercially available electrical conductive fillers were fabricated and tested. From this study it can be concluded that the new graphite nanoplatelet material is superior compared to the other fillers in terms of flexural strength and modulus of the composite. It is at least as effective as the other fillers in decreasing the coefficient of thermal expansion of the polymer matrix and it has a low percolation threshold (for the epoxy-based composites, percolation values are not yet available for the polypropylene systems). The above properties combined with the low cost of this nano-sized graphite platelets make this material a major candidate not only for structural applications but for new applications as well such as electrostatic dissipation and electro magnetic interference shielding.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Partial support for this research was provided by a grant from NASA LaRC, "Graphite Nanoreinforcements for Aerospace Nanocomposites" NAG1-01004, Thomas Gates, Program Director. The authors also wish to express their thanks to the Bassel Chemical Company for providing the polypropylene resin, Akzo Nobel Company for supplying the carbon black, and UCAR Co. for providing the acid intercalated graphite compounds.

REFERENCES

1. J.V. Milewski and H.S. Katz, "Handbook of Reinforcements for Plastics", Van Nostrand Reinold Co., New York (1987).
2. P. Bajaj, N.K. Jha, and R.A. Kumar, "Effect of Coupling Agents on the Mechanical Properties of Mica/Epoxy and Glass Fiber/ Mica/Epoxy Composites", *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, **44** 1921 (1992).
3. P. Bajaj, N.K. Jha, and R.A. Kumar, "Effect of Coupling Agents on Thermal and Electrical Properties of Mica/Epoxy Composites" *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, **56**,1339 (1995).
4. J.M. Garces, D.J. Moll, J. Bicerano, R. Fibiger, and D.G. McLeod, "Polymeric Nanocomposites for Automotive Applications", *Adv. Mater.*, **12**, 1835 (2000).
5. E.P. Giannelis, "Polymer Layered Silicate Nanocomposites", *Adv. Mater.* **8**, 1,29 (1996).
6. T.W. Ebbesen, "Carbon Nanotubes", CRR Press, Boca Raton, (1997).
7. Y.X., Pan, Z.Z. Yu, Y.C. Ou and G.H. Hu, "A New Process of Fabricating Electrically Conducting Nylon6/Graphite nanocomposites via Intercalation Polymerization" *J. Polym. Sci.*, Part B: Polym. Phy., **38**, 1626 (2002).
8. G.H. Chen, D.J. Wu, W.G., Weng, B. He and W.L., Yan, "Preparation of Polystyrene-Graphite Conducting Nanocomposites via Intercalation Plymerization", *Polym. Int.*, **50**, 980 (2001).
9. G.H. Chen, D.J. Wu, W.G., Weng, B. He and W.L., Yan, "Preparation of Polymer/Graphite Conducting Nanocomposites by an Intercalation Plymerization", *Appl. Polym. Sci.*, **82**, 2506 (2001).
10. F.M. Uhl, F.J. Lamelas, and C.A. Wilkie, "Flame Retardancy of Graphite Nanocomposites", Proc. ACS: Division of Polym. Mater. Sci., and Eng., 83, 56 (2000).
11. F.M. Uhl, and C.A. Wilkie, "Polystyrene/Graphite Nanocomposites: Effect on Thermal Stability", *Polym. Degradation and Stability*, 76,111 (2002)
12. M. Xiao, L.Y., Sun, J.J. Liu, Y. Li and K.C. Gong, "Synthesis and Properties of Polystyrene/Graphite Nanocomposites", *Polymer*, **43**, 2245 (2002)
13. H. Fukushima and L.T. Drzal, "Graphite Nanoplatelets as Rienforcements for Polymers: Structural and Electrical Properties", Proceedings of The American Society for Composites, Seventeenth Technical Conference, 160, (2002).